

Ice-shelf vibrations modeled by a full 3-D elastic model: field equations (version 8.2)

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Abstract

This version as the previous version 8.1 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17069606>) considers the modeling of the oscillation of a system consisting of three components: (i) an ice shelf, (ii) seawater in a cavity under the ice shelf and (iii) meltwater lakes filling the valleys on the ice shelf surface. The difference is in the ice shelf geometry, which corresponds to an idealized ice surface morphology with valleys and hills arranged in a checkerboard pattern. As in the previous version 8.1, this model is based on the finite volume method of approximation the momentum equations, as were considered in versions 5 and 6 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7697142>, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10252877>, <https://doi.org/10.1017/aog.2024.47>)

Both the sub-ice seawater flow and meltwater flow in lakes are treated as a “potential flow”. Accordingly, in this model, as in the previous versions 7 and 8.1, both the subglacial flow of seawater and the flow of meltwater in lakes (long gravity waves on the surface of meltwater lakes) are described by the corresponding wave equations.

This version is essentially an extension of the previous version 8.1, and the same experiments were performed with the new ice shelf geometry.

As in the previous versions, the oscillations of the three-component system were modeled for harmonic incoming pressure perturbations and for a wide range of incoming wave frequencies. As in the previous versions, the amplitude spectra obtained using the model reveal distinct resonant peaks, as were also observed in previous models. Accounting for the periodic structure of the ice shelf geometry, the obtained dispersion spectra reveal the presence of band gaps (<https://doi.org/10.3189/2012AoG60A120>) as was observed, in particular, in models applied to an ice shelf corresponding to the geometry of Ward Hunt Ice Shelf, Ellesmere Island, Canadian Arctic (<https://doi.org/10.1017/jog.2023.58>, <https://doi.org/10.1017/aog.2024.47>).

1. Model description and field equations

This item (mathematical model description) fully corresponds (and repeats it) to the item 1 from version 8.1 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17069606>).

1.1 Basic equations

1.1.1 Momentum equations described the motion of an ice shelf

In this model, ice shelf deformations are described using the momentum equations written as the momentum balance equation in the volume V (bounded by the surface S) of an elastically deformable continuous medium have the following form (e.g. [1], [2], [3], [4]) (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7697142>)

$$\frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} \int_V \rho U_i dV = \int_V \left(\frac{\partial \sigma_{ik}}{\partial x_k} + \rho g_i \right) dV \quad (1.1)$$

or

$$\frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} \int_V \rho U_i dV = \int_S \sigma_{ik} dS_k + \int_V \rho g_i dV \quad (1.2)$$

where σ is the stress tensor; and ρ is the ice density; $i, k = 1, 2, 3$ or in terms of rectangular coordinate (XYZ) i, k means x, y, z ; U_i are displacements of an elastic continuous medium (displacements of ice) which are also denoted in rectangular coordinates as U, V, W : U, V and W are two horizontal and one vertical ice displacements, respectively.

As in previous versions/models (XYZ) is a rectangular coordinate system with the X -axis along the center line, and Z -axis pointing vertically up. The ice shelf has a length L along the center line. The geometry of the ice shelf is assumed to be given by lateral boundary functions $y_{1,2}(x)$ at sides labeled 1 and 2 and functions for the surface and base elevation,

$h_{s,b}(x, y)$, denoted by subscripts s and b, respectively. Thus, the domain, which includes the volume of integration in Eqs. (1), is $\Omega = \{0 < x < L, y_1(x) < y < y_2(x), h_b(x, y) < z < h_s(x, y)\}$.

1.1.2 Wave equation described sub-ice seawater flow in the cavity

Sub-ice water is assumed to be an incompressible inviscid fluid of uniform density. Another assumption is that water depth in the cavity below the ice shelf changes gradually in the horizontal directions. Thus, the ice-front and other such features are not considered here. Moreover, the ice is considered to be a continuous solid elastic plate. Under these three assumptions, sub-ice water flow is independent of z in a vertical column. Manipulating the governing equations of the shallow sub-ice water layer yields the wave equation (<https://doi.org/10.1038/274464a0>):

$$\frac{\partial^2 W_{sl}}{\partial t^2} = \frac{1}{\rho_w} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(d_0 \frac{\partial P'}{\partial x} \right) + \frac{1}{\rho_w} \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(d_0 \frac{\partial P'}{\partial y} \right), \quad (2)$$

where ρ_w is sea water density; $d_0(x, y)$ is the depth of the sub-ice water layer; $W_{sl}(x, y, t)$ is the vertical deflection of the surface of sub-ice water layer and $W_{sl}(x, y, t) = W_b(x, y, t) = W(x, y, h_b(x, y), t)$ ($W_b(x, y, t)$ is the vertical deflection of the ice-shelf base) and $P'(x, y, t)$ is the deviation of the sub-ice water pressure from the hydrostatic value.

1.1.3 Wave equation described gravity waves on surfaces of the meltwater lakes

In this model, melt water in lakes is also considered as an incompressible inviscid fluid of uniform density. It is assumed that gravity waves in lakes are described by the wave

equation for long gravity waves. The corresponding manipulation of the governing equations for the shallow meltwater layer in the lakes yields the wave equation (e.g. [2]):

$$\frac{\partial^2 \zeta}{\partial t^2} - \frac{\partial^2 W_s}{\partial t^2} = g \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(h_0 \frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial x} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(h_0 \frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial y} \right) \right), \quad (3)$$

where $\zeta(x, y, t)$ is the vertical deflection of the water surface in lakes (from the equilibrium surface level); $h_0(x, y)$ is the depth of the meltwater lakes; $W_s(x, y, t)$ is the vertical deflection of the ice-shelf surface, and $W_s(x, y, t) = W(x, y, h_s(x, y), t)$.

1.2 Boundary conditions

The boundary conditions for equations (1) are:

- (i) stress free ice surface and normal stress exerted by meltwater in regions on the ice surface where there are meltwater lakes;
- (ii) the normal stress exerted by seawater at the ice-shelf free edges and at the ice-shelf base; and
- (iii) rigidly fixed edges at the grounding line of the ice-shelf.

In this model, the boundary conditions are also (as in previous versions) considered as a linear combination

$$\alpha_1 F_i(U, V, W) + \alpha_2 \Phi_i(U, V, W) = 0, \quad i = 1, 2, 3, \quad (4)$$

where:

- (i) $F_i(U, V, W) = 0$ is the typical and well-known form of the boundary conditions where, for example, the condition on the ice-shelf surface is expressed as $\sigma_{ik} n_k = 0$ or $\sigma_{ik} n_k = -P_w n_i$ (\vec{n} is the unit vector normal to the surface, P_w is the meltwater pressure);
- (ii) $\Phi_i(U, V, W) = 0$ is the approximation based on the application of a *finite volume approach* to the approximation of the boundary conditions, taking in to account for the typical form of boundary conditions on the boundaries of an *elementary volume* (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10252877>);
and
- (iii) the coefficients α_1 and α_2 satisfy the condition $\alpha_1 + \alpha_2 = 1$.

The boundary conditions for the subglacial seawater layer (for equation (2)) correspond to a frontal gravity incident ocean wave. They are

- (i) at $x = 0$: $\frac{\partial P'}{\partial x} = 0$;
- (ii) at $y = y_1, y = y_2$: $\frac{\partial P'}{\partial y} = 0$;
- (iii) at $x = L$: $P' = A_0 \rho_w g e^{i\omega t}$, where A_0 is the amplitude of the incident wave.

The boundary conditions for equation (3) correspond to the assumption that along the coastlines of the meltwater lakes the vertical deflection of the water surface $\zeta(x, y, t)$ is approximately equal to the vertical deflection of the ice-shelf surface $W_s(x, y, t)$, i.e. the boundary conditions are $\zeta(x, y, t) = W_s(x, y, t)$ along the coastlines.

1.3 Discretization of the model

Numerical solutions were obtained by a finite volume method, which is based on the standard coordinate transformation $x, y, z \rightarrow x, \eta = \frac{y-y_1}{y_2-y_1}, \xi = (h_s - z)/H$, where H is the ice thickness ($H = h_s - h_b$). The coordinate transformation maps the ice domain Ω into the rectangular parallelepiped $\Pi = \{0 \leq x \leq L; 0 \leq \eta \leq 1; 0 \leq \xi \leq 1\}$, which simplifies the numerical discretization.

A detailed description of the approximation of the momentum equations (1) was presented in version 5 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7697142>).

1.4 Equations for ice-shelf displacements

Constitutive relationships between stress tensor components and displacements correspond to Hooke's law (e.g., [3], [4]):

$$\sigma_{ij} = \frac{E}{1+\nu} \left(u_{ij} + \frac{\nu}{1-2\nu} u_{ll} \delta_{ij} \right) , \quad (5)$$

where u_{ij} are the strain components, E - Young's modulus, ν - Poisson's ratio.

1.5 Ice-shelf harmonic vibrations. The eigenvalue problem.

(Essentially, this point repeats the assumptions made in previous versions [6-9]. All assumptions of this point that were valid for the previous models, are also valid for the model considered here)

It is assumed that for harmonic vibrations all variables are periodic in time, with the periodicity of the incident wave (of the forcing) given by the frequency ω , i.e.,

$$\tilde{\zeta}(x, y, z, t) = \zeta(x, y, z) e^{i\omega t}, \quad (7)$$

where $\tilde{\zeta} = \{U, V, W, \sigma_{ij}, \zeta\}$,

where we are interested in the real part of the variables expressed in complex form.

This assumption also implies that the full solution of the linear partial differential Eqs. (1), (2), (3) is a sum of the solution for the steady-state flexure of the ice shelf and solution (7) for the time-dependent problem. In other words, solution (7) implies that the deformation due to the gravitational forcing can be separated from the vibration problem, i.e. the term ρg in the third equation from (1) as well as the appropriate terms in the boundary conditions (4) are absent from the final equations formulated for the vibration problem, because a time-independent solution accounting for them applies and is not of interest in this study.

The separation of variables in Eq. (7) and its substitution into Eqs. (1), (2), (3) yields the same equations, but with the operator $\frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2}$ replaced with the constant $-\omega^2$, i.e. we obtain equation for $\zeta(x, y, z)$:

$$\mathcal{L} \zeta = -\omega^2 \zeta, \tag{8}$$

where \mathcal{L} is a linear partial differential operator.

The numerical solution of Eq. (8) at different values of ω yields the dependence of ζ on the frequency of the forcing ω . When the frequency of the forcing converges to the eigenfrequency of the system, we observe the typical rapid increase of deformation/stresses in the spectra in the form of the resonant peaks.

Note that here, the term “eigenvalue” refers to the eigenfrequency (ω_n) of the ice/water system or corresponding periodicity ($T_n = \frac{2\pi}{\omega_n}$). As mentioned previously, the term “eigenvalue” is employed in the same meaning like in a Sturm-Liouville Eigenvalue Problem (e.g. [10]). Eigenvalues (where resonant peaks would be observed) are denoted by the letters ω_n or T_n with the subscript n (or other), which is integer, because the array of the eigenvalues is a countable set.

Letters ω or T without the subscript denote the non-resonant values of frequency or periodicity of the ice/water system. They are defined by the frequency of the incident wave (of the forcing).

The eigenvalues can be derived from the equation $D(\omega) = 0$, where D is the determinant of the matrix, which results from the discretization of Eq. (8) and of the corresponding boundary conditions. However, the probability of the appearance of the forcing at any specific frequency is practically zero. This can be seen when we consider only events within the frequency range $(\omega_i - \Delta\omega, \omega_i + \Delta\omega)$. The probability of a forcing that is within the frequency range, is non-zero:

$$p\{\omega \in (\omega_i - \Delta\omega, \omega_i + \Delta\omega)\} = \frac{2\Delta\omega}{\Omega}, \quad (9)$$

where Ω is the width of the range in omega space, which includes all possible frequencies of the forcing. Eq. (9) also assumes that the events have equal probabilities in different parts of Ω .

Thus, the probability of the resonant-like motion is higher when the value $\Delta\omega$, which is defined by the width of the resonant peak, is higher too. Therefore, the width of the resonant peaks is an important parameter, from a practical standpoint, because it defines the probability of the suitable resonant-like motion.

Computation of the spectra, such as provided below, thus provides important information about the width of resonant peaks within the likely range of forcing frequencies found in nature. By assessing the widths of such peaks, a better understanding of the probability that any one specific forcing event, at a specific ω can be assessed.

2. Code input parameters and code output results

The numerical experiments with forced vibrations were undertaken for a physically idealized ice shelf with the geometry shown in Figure 1. In the undeformed ice shelf, the four edges had coordinates $x = 0, x = L, y_1 = 0, y_2 = B$, where L is the plate length along the x -axis and B is the plate width along the y -axis ($B = y_2 - y_1$, see equations (1)).

The ice plate had only one fixed edge (at $x = 0$), while the other edges (at $x = L, y_1 = 0, y_2 = B$) were free. This is the special case of an ice shelf, which is also known as an “ice tongue” (<https://doi.org/10.1038/274464a0>). The intact ice tongue was 2 km in longitudinal extent, 0.2 km width.

The ice surface morphology with valleys and hills arranged periodically in a checkerboard pattern, was modeled using sinusoidally varying ice thickness in the X and Y directions

$$H(x) = H_0 + A_H \frac{\rho_w}{\rho} \cos\left(\frac{2\pi x}{\Delta l_x}\right) \cdot \sin\left(\frac{2\pi y}{\Delta l_y}\right), \quad (10)$$

where A_H is the amplitude of ice thickness oscillations, which was considered as a parameter of the models; $\Delta l_x, \Delta l_y$ is the spatial periodicities of the ice shelf geometry (Δl_x in the model was equal to 0.5 km and Δl_y was equal to 0.2 km); H_0 in the models was equal to 25m. (The aspect ratio (ice thickness/ice length) for the ice shelf in this version is the same as in the previous version 8.1).

The parameters of the ice shelf with surface morphology with valleys and hills arranged periodically in a checkerboard pattern are listed in the **lines 32-34** of the program code. They are

- a) the spatial periodicities of the ice shelf geometry in the X and Y directions Δl_x and Δl_y , respectively (designated as T_CrX and T_CrY in the code)

- b) the amplitude of ice thickness oscillations depth A_H (designated as *Depth_Cr* in the code);

In accordance with equation (10), **lines 150-154** of the code define the ice surface morphology (sinusoidally varying ice thickness).

Figure 2 shows how the depth of meltwater lakes filling the valleys changes along the ice shelf surface with valleys and hills arranged periodically in a checkerboard pattern. The steady (undisturbed) level/height of the surface of meltwater lakes is determined by the parameter L_{Lakes} in **line 37** of the code. According to the value of the L_{Lakes} parameter, the depth of meltwater lakes is determined (h_0 in equation (3)) in **lines 202-240** of the code.

As in the previous version 8.1, in this model, the area of definition of the function $\zeta(x, y, t)$ (Eq. (3)) is expanded to the entire region where the ice is located: $0 < x < L; y_1(x) < y < y_2(x)$. That is, the function $\zeta(x, y, t)$ is vertical deflection of the water surface in lakes where there are meltwater lakes (where $h_s(x, y) < L_{Lakes}$), and $\zeta(x, y, t)$ is vertical displacement of the ice shelf surface, i.e. $\zeta(x, y, t) = W_s(x, y, t)$ for $h_s(x, y) > L_{Lakes}$. The function $\zeta(x, y, t)$ is defined in **lines 734-1005** of the code. Compared to the previous version 8.1, some changes have been made to the code. These changes imply that the coastlines of the meltwater lakes are located entirely within the region $\Omega = \{0 < x < L; y_1(x) < y < y_2(x)\}$, i.e. in the region that determines the extent of the ice shelf in the X and Y directions, respectively.

As in the previous versions 7 and 8.1, the main cycle (**lines 684-38441**), in which the frequency of the incident wave (forcing) is varied, includes (i) the code where the solution of equation (3) is obtained (**lines 810-860**); (ii) the code that provides the solution to the momentum equations (1) (**lines 1009-38186**) and (iii) the code that provides the solution to the equation (2) (**lines 38212-38359**). Accordingly, having determined the maximum value of the vertical displacement of the ice shelf (**lines 38426-38432**) (or

maximum value of free energy) for different values of the frequency of the forcing we obtain the amplitude spectrum (or energy spectrum).

Figures 3-92 show a) the function $\zeta(x, y, \omega)$, i.e. the vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes, - in the corresponding mode obtained for a given periodicity/frequency; b) ice shelf base vertical deflection; c) the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$, where $W_s(x, y, \omega)$ is the vertical deflection of the ice shelf surface.

Figures 3-17 show a series of results obtained for the amplitude of ice thickness oscillations $A_H = 12 \text{ m}$ and for $\alpha_1 = 1.0, \alpha_2 = 0.0$ (**pages 16-30**).

Figures 18-32 show a series of results obtained for the amplitude of ice thickness oscillations $A_H = 12 \text{ m}$ and for $\alpha_1 = 0.0, \alpha_2 = 1.0$ (**pages 31-45**).

Figures 33-47 show a series of results obtained for the amplitude of ice thickness oscillations $A_H = 14 \text{ m}$ and for $\alpha_1 = 1.0, \alpha_2 = 0.0$ (**pages 46-60**).

Figures 48-62 show a series of results obtained for the amplitude of ice thickness oscillations $A_H = 14 \text{ m}$ and for $\alpha_1 = 0.0, \alpha_2 = 1.0$ (**pages 61-75**).

Figures 63-77 show a series of results obtained for the amplitude of ice thickness oscillations $A_H = 16 \text{ m}$ and for $\alpha_1 = 1.0, \alpha_2 = 0.0$ (**pages 76-90**).

Figures 78-92 show a series of results obtained for the amplitude of ice thickness oscillations $A_H = 16 \text{ m}$ and for $\alpha_1 = 0.0, \alpha_2 = 1.0$ (**pages 91-105**).

The output results of the code are the amplitude spectra (the amplitude of the ice shelf versus periodicity/frequency of the forcing): [lines 38449-38513](#)

In particular, **Figure 93** show the amplitude spectra obtained in experiments, when meltwater lakes were present on the ice shelf surface (**pages 106-107**).

Figure 94 show the dispersion spectra obtained in the experiments with different values of the amplitude A_H of ice thickness oscillations and with meltwater lakes on ice shelf surface (**page 108**). These experiments also reveal Bragg scattering for the periodic structure of ice shelf geometry with a checkerboard morphology of the ice surface of valleys and hills.

Fig. 1a

Fig. 1b

Fig. 1c

Figure 1. The ice-shelf surface **(a)** and ice shelf base **(b)** and sea bottom **(c)** considered in the numerical experiments. The amplitude of ice thickness oscillations $A_H = 16 \text{ m}$ (equation (10)). The spatial periodicity (Δl_x) in X -direction is equal to 0.5 km , the spatial periodicity (Δl_y) in Y -direction is equal to 0.2 km .

Fig. 2a

Fig. 2b

Fig. 2c

Figure 2. The meltwater lakes depth on the ice shelf surface: **(a)** - $A_H = 8$ m; **(b)** - $A_H = 12$ m; **(c)** $A_H = 18$ m.

Amplitude of ice thickness oscillations $A_H = 12\text{ m}$ (see Figure 1).

$$\alpha_1 = 1.0, \alpha_2 = 0.0.$$

Fig. 3a

Fig. 3b

Fig. 3c

Figure 3. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 10\text{ s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0, \alpha_2 = 0.0; A_H = 12\text{ m}$.

Fig. 4a

Fig. 4b

Fig. 4c

Figure 4. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 15\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0$, $\alpha_2 = 0.0$; $A_H = 12\text{ m}$.

Fig. 5a

Fig. 5b

Fig. 5c

Figure 5. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 20s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0$, $\alpha_2 = 0.0$; $A_H = 12 m$.

Fig. 6a

Fig. 6b

Fig. 6c

Figure 6. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 25s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0$, $\alpha_2 = 0.0$; $A_H = 12 m$.

Fig. 7a

Fig. 7b

Fig. 7c

Figure 7. a) vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 30s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0$, $\alpha_2 = 0.0$; $A_H = 12 m$.

Fig. 8a

Fig. 8b

Fig. 8c

Figure 8. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 40\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0$, $\alpha_2 = 0.0$; $A_H = 12\text{ m}$.

Fig. 9a

Fig. 9b

Fig. 9c

Figure 9. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 50s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0$, $\alpha_2 = 0.0$; $A_H = 12 m$.

Fig. 10a

Fig. 10b

Fig. 10c

Figure 10. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 60s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0, \alpha_2 = 0.0; A_H = 12 m$.

Fig. 11a

Fig. 11b

Fig. 11c

Figure 11. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 70s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0$, $\alpha_2 = 0.0$; $A_H = 12 m$.

Fig. 12a

Fig. 12b

Fig. 12c

Figure 12. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 80\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0, \alpha_2 = 0.0; A_H = 12\text{ m}$.

Fig. 13a

Fig. 13b

Fig. 13c

Figure 13. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 90s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0, \alpha_2 = 0.0; A_H = 12 m$.

Fig. 14a

Fig. 14b

Fig. 14c

Figure 14. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 110s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0, \alpha_2 = 0.0; A_H = 12 m$.

Fig. 15a

Fig. 15b

Fig. 15c

Figure 15. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 130s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0, \alpha_2 = 0.0; A_H = 12 m$.

Fig. 16a

Fig. 16b

Fig. 16c

Figure 16. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 150s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0, \alpha_2 = 0.0; A_H = 12 m$.

Fig. 17a

Fig. 17b

Fig. 17c

Figure 17. a) vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 170s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0, \alpha_2 = 0.0; A_H = 12 m$.

Amplitude of ice thickness oscillations $A_H = 12\text{ m}$ (see Figure 1).

$$\alpha_1 = 0.0, \alpha_2 = 1.0.$$

Fig. 18a

Fig. 18b

Fig. 18c

Figure 18. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 10\text{ s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0, \alpha_2 = 1.0; A_H = 12\text{ m}$.

Fig. 19a

Fig. 19b

Fig. 19c

Figure 19. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 15\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0$, $\alpha_2 = 1.0$; $A_H = 12\text{ m}$.

Fig. 20a

Fig. 20b

Fig. 20c

Figure 20. a) vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 20s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0, \alpha_2 = 1.0; A_H = 12 m$.

Fig. 21a

Fig. 21b

Fig. 21c

Figure 21. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 25\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0$, $\alpha_2 = 1.0$; $A_H = 12\text{ m}$.

Fig. 22a

Fig. 22b

Fig. 22c

Figure 22. a) vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 30s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0, \alpha_2 = 1.0; A_H = 12 m$.

Fig. 23a

Fig. 23b

Fig. 23c

Figure 23. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 40\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0, \alpha_2 = 1.0; A_H = 12\text{ m}$.

Fig. 24a

Fig. 24b

Fig. 24c

Figure 24. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 50s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0$, $\alpha_2 = 1.0$; $A_H = 12 m$.

Fig. 25a

Fig. 25b

Fig. 25c

Figure 25. a) vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 60\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0, \alpha_2 = 1.0; A_H = 12\text{ m}$.

Fig. 26a

Fig. 26b

Fig. 26c

Figure 26. a) vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 70\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0$, $\alpha_2 = 1.0$; $A_H = 12\text{ m}$.

Fig. 27a

Fig. 27b

Fig. 27c

Figure 27. a) vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 80s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0, \alpha_2 = 1.0; A_H = 12 m$.

Fig. 28a

Fig. 28b

Fig. 28c

Figure 28. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 90s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0, \alpha_2 = 1.0; A_H = 12 m$.

Fig. 29a

Fig. 29b

Fig. 29c

Figure 29. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 110s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0, \alpha_2 = 1.0; A_H = 12 m$.

Fig. 30a

Fig. 30b

Fig. 30c

Figure 30. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 130\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0$, $\alpha_2 = 1.0$; $A_H = 12\text{ m}$.

Fig. 31a

Fig. 31b

Fig. 31c

Figure 31. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 150s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0, \alpha_2 = 1.0; A_H = 12 m$.

Fig. 32a

Fig. 32b

Fig. 32c

Figure 32. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 170s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0, \alpha_2 = 1.0; A_H = 12 m$.

Amplitude of ice thickness oscillations $A_H = 14 \text{ m}$ (see Figure 1).

$$\alpha_1 = 1.0, \alpha_2 = 0.0$$

Fig. 33a

Fig. 33b

Fig. 33c

Figure 33. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 10 \text{ s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0, \alpha_2 = 0.0; A_H = 14 \text{ m}$.

Fig. 34a

Fig. 34b

Fig. 34c

Figure 34. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 15\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0$, $\alpha_2 = 0.0$; $A_H = 14\text{ m}$.

Fig. 35a

Fig. 35b

Fig. 35c

Figure 35. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 20\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0, \alpha_2 = 0.0; A_H = 14\text{ m}$.

Fig. 36a

Fig. 36b

Fig. 36c

Figure 36. a) vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 25\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0, \alpha_2 = 0.0; A_H = 14\text{ m}$.

Fig. 37a

Fig. 37b

Fig. 37c

Figure 37. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 30\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0, \alpha_2 = 0.0; A_H = 14\text{ m}$.

Fig. 38a

Fig. 38b

Fig. 38c

Figure 38. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 40\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0$, $\alpha_2 = 0.0$; $A_H = 14\text{ m}$.

Fig. 39a

Fig. 39b

Fig. 39c

Figure 39. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 50\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0, \alpha_2 = 0.0; A_H = 14\text{ m}$.

Fig. 40a

Fig. 40b

Fig. 40c

Figure 40. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 60\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0, \alpha_2 = 0.0; A_H = 14\text{ m}$.

Fig. 41a

Fig. 41b

Fig. 41c

Figure 41. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 70\text{ s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0$, $\alpha_2 = 0.0$; $A_H = 14\text{ m}$.

Fig. 42a

Fig. 42b

Fig. 42c

Figure 42. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 80\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0$, $\alpha_2 = 0.0$; $A_H = 14\text{ m}$.

Fig. 43a

Fig. 43b

Fig. 43c

Figure 43. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 90s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0, \alpha_2 = 0.0; A_H = 14 m$.

Fig. 44a

Fig. 44b

Fig. 44c

Figure 44. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 110s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0$, $\alpha_2 = 0.0$; $A_H = 14 m$.

Fig. 45a

Fig. 45b

Fig. 45c

Figure 45. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 130s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0$, $\alpha_2 = 0.0$; $A_H = 14 m$.

Fig. 46a

Fig. 46b

Fig. 46c

Figure 46. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 150s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0$, $\alpha_2 = 0.0$; $A_H = 14 m$.

Fig. 47a

Fig. 47b

Fig. 47c

Figure 47. a) vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 170s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0, \alpha_2 = 0.0; A_H = 14 m$.

Amplitude of ice thickness oscillations $A_H = 14 \text{ m}$ (see Figure 1).

$$\alpha_1 = 0.0, \alpha_2 = 1.0$$

Fig. 48a

Fig. 48b

Fig. 48c

Figure 48. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 10 \text{ s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0, \alpha_2 = 1.0$; $A_H = 14 \text{ m}$.

Fig. 49a

Fig. 49b

Fig. 49c

Figure 49. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 15\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0$, $\alpha_2 = 1.0$; $A_H = 14\text{ m}$.

Fig. 50a

Fig. 50b

Fig. 50c

Figure 50. a) vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 20\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0, \alpha_2 = 1.0; A_H = 14\text{ m}$.

Fig. 51a

Fig. 51b

Fig. 51c

Figure 51. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 25\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0, \alpha_2 = 1.0; A_H = 14\text{ m}$.

Fig. 52a

Fig. 52b

Fig. 52c

Figure 52. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 30\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0, \alpha_2 = 1.0; A_H = 14\text{ m}$.

Fig. 53a

Fig. 53b

Fig. 53c

Figure 53. a) vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 40\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0$, $\alpha_2 = 1.0$; $A_H = 14\text{ m}$.

Fig. 54a

Fig. 54b

Fig. 54c

Figure 54. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 50\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0$, $\alpha_2 = 1.0$; $A_H = 14\text{ m}$.

Fig. 55a

Fig. 55b

Fig. 55c

Figure 55. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 60\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0$, $\alpha_2 = 1.0$; $A_H = 14\text{ m}$.

Fig. 56a

Fig. 56b

Fig. 56c

Figure 56. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 70\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0, \alpha_2 = 1.0; A_H = 14\text{ m}$.

Fig. 57a

Fig. 57b

Fig. 57c

Figure 57. a) vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 80\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0, \alpha_2 = 1.0; A_H = 14\text{ m}$.

Fig. 58a

Fig. 58b

Fig. 58c

Figure 58. a) vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 90\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0, \alpha_2 = 1.0; A_H = 14\text{ m}$.

Fig. 59a

Fig. 59b

Fig. 59c

Figure 59. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 110s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0, \alpha_2 = 1.0; A_H = 14 m$.

Fig. 60a

Fig. 60b

Fig. 60c

Figure 60. a) vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 130s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0$, $\alpha_2 = 1.0$; $A_H = 14 m$.

Fig. 61a

Fig. 61b

Fig. 61c

Figure 61. a) vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 150s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0$, $\alpha_2 = 1.0$; $A_H = 14 m$.

Fig. 62a

Fig. 62b

Fig. 62c

Figure 62. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 170s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0$, $\alpha_2 = 1.0$; $A_H = 14 m$.

Amplitude of ice thickness oscillations $A_H = 16\text{ m}$ (see Figure 1).

$$\alpha_1 = 1.0, \alpha_2 = 0.0$$

Fig. 63a

Fig. 63b

Fig. 63c

Figure 63. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 10\text{ s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0, \alpha_2 = 0.0; A_H = 16\text{ m}$.

Fig. 64a

Fig. 64b

Fig. 64c

Figure 64. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 15\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0, \alpha_2 = 0.0; A_H = 16\text{ m}$.

Fig. 65a

Fig. 65b

Fig. 65c

Figure 65. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 20\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0$, $\alpha_2 = 0.0$; $A_H = 16\text{ m}$.

Fig. 66a

Fig. 66b

Fig. 66c

Figure 66. a) vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 25\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0, \alpha_2 = 0.0; A_H = 16\text{ m}$.

Fig. 67a

Fig. 67b

Fig. 67c

Figure 67. a) vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 30s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0, \alpha_2 = 0.0; A_H = 16 m$.

Fig. 68a

Fig. 68b

Fig. 68c

Figure 68. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 40s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0, \alpha_2 = 0.0; A_H = 16 m$.

Fig. 69a

Fig. 69b

Fig. 69c

Figure 69. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 50s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0$, $\alpha_2 = 0.0$; $A_H = 16 m$.

Fig. 70a

Fig. 70b

Fig. 70c

Figure 70. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 60\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0, \alpha_2 = 0.0; A_H = 16\text{ m}$.

Fig. 71a

Fig. 71b

Fig. 71c

Figure 71. a) vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 70\text{ s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0, \alpha_2 = 0.0; A_H = 16\text{ m}$.

Fig. 72a

Fig. 72b

Fig. 72c

Figure 72. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 80s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0, \alpha_2 = 0.0; A_H = 16 m$.

Fig. 73a

Fig. 73b

Fig. 73c

Figure 73. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 90\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0$, $\alpha_2 = 0.0$; $A_H = 16\text{ m}$.

Fig. 74a

Fig. 74b

Fig. 74c

Figure 74. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 110s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0, \alpha_2 = 0.0; A_H = 16 m$.

Fig. 75a

Fig. 75b

Fig. 75c

Figure 75. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 130s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0, \alpha_2 = 0.0; A_H = 16 m$.

Fig. 76a

Fig. 76b

Fig. 76c

Figure 76. a) vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 150s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0, \alpha_2 = 0.0; A_H = 16 m$.

Fig. 77a

Fig. 77b

Fig. 77c

Figure 77. a) vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 170s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0, \alpha_2 = 0.0; A_H = 16 m$.

Amplitude of ice thickness oscillations $A_H = 16 \text{ m}$ (see Figure 1).

$$\alpha_1 = 0.0, \alpha_2 = 1.0$$

Fig. 78a

Fig. 78b

Fig. 78c

Figure 78. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 10 \text{ s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0, \alpha_2 = 1.0; A_H = 16 \text{ m}$.

Fig. 79a

Fig. 79b

Fig. 79c

Figure 79. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 15\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0$, $\alpha_2 = 1.0$; $A_H = 16\text{ m}$.

Fig. 80a

Fig. 80b

Fig. 80c

Figure 80. a) vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 20\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0$, $\alpha_2 = 1.0$; $A_H = 16\text{ m}$.

Fig. 81a

Fig. 81b

Fig. 81c

Figure 81. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 25\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0$, $\alpha_2 = 1.0$; $A_H = 16\text{ m}$.

Fig. 82a

Fig. 82b

Fig. 82c

Figure 82. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 30\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0$, $\alpha_2 = 1.0$; $A_H = 16\text{ m}$.

Fig. 83a

Fig. 83b

Fig. 83c

Figure 83. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 40\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0, \alpha_2 = 1.0; A_H = 16\text{ m}$.

Fig. 84a

Fig. 84b

Fig. 84c

Figure 84. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 50s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0, \alpha_2 = 1.0; A_H = 16 m$.

Fig. 85a

Fig. 85b

Fig. 85c

Figure 85. a) vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 60\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0$, $\alpha_2 = 1.0$; $A_H = 16\text{ m}$.

Fig. 86a

Fig. 86b

Fig. 86c

Figure 86. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 70\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0$, $\alpha_2 = 1.0$; $A_H = 16\text{ m}$.

Fig. 87a

Fig. 87b

Fig. 87c

Figure 87. a) vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 80s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0$, $\alpha_2 = 1.0$; $A_H = 16 m$.

Fig. 88a

Fig. 88b

Fig. 88c

Figure 88. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 90\text{s}$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0, \alpha_2 = 1.0; A_H = 16\text{ m}$.

Fig. 89a

Fig. 89b

Fig. 89c

Figure 89. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 110s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0, \alpha_2 = 1.0; A_H = 16 m$.

Fig. 90a

Fig. 90b

Fig. 90c

Figure 90. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 130s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0$, $\alpha_2 = 1.0$; $A_H = 16 m$.

Fig. 91a

Fig. 91b

Fig. 91c

Figure 91. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 150s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0, \alpha_2 = 1.0; A_H = 16 m$.

Fig. 92a

Fig. 92b

Fig. 92c

Figure 92. **a)** vertical deflection of the surface of the system: ice shelf and meltwater lakes ($\zeta(x, y, \omega)$) **b)** ice shelf base vertical deflection; **c)** the difference $\zeta(x, y, \omega) - W_s(x, y, \omega)$. The periodicity of the forcing $T = 170s$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 0.0$, $\alpha_2 = 1.0$; $A_H = 16 m$.

Fig. 93a

Fig. 93b

Fig. 93c

Fig. 93d

Fig. 93e

Figure 93. The amplitude spectra obtained in the experiments, when there were the meltwater lakes on ice shelf surface: **a)** $A_H = 10m$; **b)** $A_H = 12m$; **c)** $A_H = 14m$; **d)** $A_H = 16m$ **e)** $A_H = 18m$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0, \alpha_2 = 0.0$. $L_{Lakes} = 2.0..2.1m$

Fig. 94a

Fig. 94b

Figure 94 The dispersion spectra obtained in the experiments, when there were the meltwater lakes on ice shelf surface: **a)** the area of the second band gap; **b)** the area of the first band gap. Curves: **1)** $A_H = 12m$; **2)** $A_H = 14m$; **3)** $A_H = 16m$; **4)** $A_H = 18m$. The parameters of the model are $\alpha_1 = 1.0$, $\alpha_2 = 0.0$

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